

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TALENT ACQUISITION EXPERIENCE AND EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT IN IT SECTOR-AN INTEGRATIVE REVIEW

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Abstract

Purpose: This paper examines existing literature to explore possible links between employee engagement (EE) and talent acquisition (TA) experience using a service quality framework within the IT industry and create congruence between the recruiter and the candidate perception to build service value. **Design:** This study is a literature review based on Toracco, R.J. (2005) and Callahan, J.L. (2010) integrative framework. Further, we distilled the search using four steps: planning, structured search, evaluating rationale, analysis and reporting, resulting in the selection of 95 articles from various databases using Zotero software. **Findings-** TA experience attributes such as reliability, responsiveness, empathy, and trust perceived during the interaction between candidates and the recruitment process throughout the recruitment cycle may influence EE in IT. Further, we propose a transdisciplinary framework to build congruence between the candidate and recruiter perceptions for strengthening the association. **Implications:** This review proposes a theoretical framework to explore the impact and strength of the relationship between TA experience and EE by applying a service quality framework. Practical implications. HR leaders can operationalize EE through routine HR practices like TA at the very onset. **Originality:** We extended existing engagement literature by proposing a new engagement driver, Talent Acquisition. Further, the review proposes a framework for building congruence between the recruiter and recruit perceptions to operationalize and sustain positive TA experiences throughout the recruitment cycle. Focuses on new relationships between TA and EE using a transdisciplinary framework of HRM and service quality. Thereby enhancing its strategic potential

Keywords: employee engagement, talent acquisition, candidate experience, recruitment, service quality.

INTRODUCTION

India is an attractive destination for IT services owing to its large pool of highly skilled technical professionals (Varma et al., 2005). It is commanding a 55% share in the global market for IT services (Rao & Balasubrahmanya., 2017). Since competition for talent is as fierce as that of customers (Berthon et al., 2005), employers have to be perceived as attractive to prospective applicants and current employees (Lievens & High house, 2003). Hence, progressive organizations can initiate the relationship during the talent acquisition process rather than waiting for the operation of building association and engagement post joining. These initiative ensures creating and sustaining long-term organization attractiveness as a 'good place to work. Attrition in India's IT sector stands at around 15-20 per cent, amplified at the lower and mid-management levels (Friedmann et al., 2008; Pallathadka, 2021). This often leads

to competition and poaching of employees (Rao, P. 2010; Lo, J. 2015); Further, the study by (O'Boyle and Harter, 2013) based on Gallup (2013) framework found only nine per cent of the Indian IT workforce is engaged. Moreover, recruitment is critical for an organization's success and existence (Parbudyal & Dale, 2003). The Indian IT firms are aware of the importance of employee engagement, branding, marketing, advertising, internet tools, job titles, compensation packages, job amenities, as means of organizational attractiveness and treat it as a business issue (Bhatt et al.,2019; Van Riemsdijk et al.,2013; Lim and Ling 2012; O zbag! et al., 2013; Asgharian et al., 2013).

However, although engagement has been around for almost three decades, there is a surprising lack of empirical research on why specific HRM-like selections lead to engagement (Ostroff & Bowen, 2016; Inceoglu & Warr, 2011). Moreover, subsequent qualitative or quantitative research between HRM and engagement is limited (Albrecht et al., 2015). Thus, the existing gap between organizations' interest in employee engagement and talent acquisition experience in IT industry deserves the required scholarship for examining this topic and justifies this study. Therefore, the three-pronged purpose of this review is (a) to explore and scrutinize extant literature for the possibility of a relationship between employee engagement and talent acquisition experience by applying the service quality framework; Furthermore, (b) create congruence between the recruiter and the candidate perception to create service value (c) propose a theoretical framework with implications for testing and future practice.

We have structured the remaining review into three sections.1. Method of literature Selection criteria 2. Transdisciplinary literature review on the need and drivers of engagement in general and IT sector; the need for talent acquisition experience and service quality in IT sector. 3. The last section discusses the review's findings, the proposed theoretical model and it's practical and research implications, followed by limitations.

1. METHODS

The current study adopted an integrative literature review by Toracco, R.J. (2005) and Callahan, J.L. (2010) to examine and explore an extant body of literature between talent acquisition experience and employee engagement by applying a service quality framework to propose new knowledge and insights. We distilled the search using four steps: planning, structured search, evaluating rationale, analysis and reporting. Finally, we conducted a broad review of employee engagement, talent acquisition and service quality using a multidisciplinary approach detailed below.

1.1 Planning:

How and where the literature was discovered. Identifying databases, search engines, and the keywords to be considered.

The literature search took place in April 2022 using various databases (e.g., Google Scholar, Elsevier, Springer, Wiley, EBSCO, Scopus, Emerald, Taylor & Francis, Springer, PsycINFO, ERIC). Further, keywords were used singularly or in combination to search the relevant databases. They include "employee engagement(EE) and HRM", "Talent acquisition

experience", "sustaining EE", "Talent acquisition in IT", "Antecedents of Employee Engagement", "employee engagement in IT", "employee engagement Literature Review" "Service quality and EE", and "TA and service quality" to was conducted independently to cast a wide net on existing literature. Additionally, only studies done between "1988 and 2021" were included in the review. Papers published in the English language were the other criteria selected. A total of 2017 studies were extracted at this initial stage. An additional screening included removing duplicates that appeared in each database using Zotero.

1.2 Search Criteria:

For quality review, we confined our search only to peer-reviewed articles published. Downloaded all the referencing information onto Microsoft excel and assigned a distinctive number. Further, Zotero was utilized to import 2017 items of literature, leveraging ten databases. Additionally, Zotero's 'duplication' function reduced this number to 1168 items. Further, filtration was based on the following criteria (e.g. 'dated before 1988', 'not in the English language, 'empirical but study design does not include employees', 'opinion piece only' and 'item unrelated to research questions).

1.3 Evaluation: rationale for Inclusion

849 out of 2017 items identified were excluded because of duplication. The grounds of exclusion included applying the term "engagement" and "talent" as generic words only without relevance; literature was not peer-reviewed, duplicated or other than English or abstract did not have any relevance to employee engagement, talent acquisition or recruitment or selection). After identifying relevance, we analyzed the full text and determined whether the article investigated the intensity of association empirically or conceptually. Additionally, we screened articles for their in-depth discussion, rather than cursory details, and their peer-reviewed status in ABDC journals with at least ten citations. Out of these 1168 items, 852 do not meet the above criteria. Eventually, 316 papers were considered for further review; however, we excluded 217 for quality and applicability (e.g. alignment of engagement, talent acquisition, with other concepts such as service quality, talent management, and corporate social responsibility). This left a total of 97 items to be included for full data extraction. We initiated the review process on April 14, 2022. Figure 1 shows inclusion and exclusion at every stage.

Fig 1: Search and Evaluation Process for Literature Selection

PRISMA-style flow of information through Stages 1–3 of the synthesis

1.4: Data organization and analysis: Final count of the number of articles

We summarized, analyzed, and synthesized the 95 articles and classified them on different subjects and research type empirical or conceptual studies. The figures 2 and 3 illustrate the distribution of the selected literature summary over time. This overview includes authors, purposes, key findings and implications, and sample information. We then examined the possible interaction between engagement and other variables. Subsequently, TA in IT and the relevance of the service quality framework are discussed. Furthermore, eight articles focusing on employee engagement and talent acquisition in IT mentioned in the bibliography of reviewed articles were synthesized using a snowballing approach.

Figure 2: Overview of Research Paper Extracted

This overview details the literature extracted based on Toracco, R.J. (2005) and Callahan, J.L. (2010) framework, resulting in the selection of 95 articles for further review: 27 empirical articles and 17 conceptual articles on EE in general; 17 empirical articles and 5 conceptual articles on TA; 5 empirical; 3 conceptual articles on service quality; and 11 empirical and 10 conceptual articles on link between HRM& EE.

Figure3: Distribution of EE publication across the years

We have outlined the distribution of 27 empirical and conceptual studies between 1990 and 2021 included in the literature review.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Co-relation between HRM & Other Interventions on Employee Engagement (EE)

Since the issue is under-researched, we have considered both conceptual and empirical analyses to review the association between HRM, and other interventions on EE in the service industry...

Summary of the correlation between HRM and EE Table 1

Author	Journal	Topic	Findings/ Summary
1.(Alola and Alafeshat 2021)	Journal of Public Affairs	The impact of human resource practices on employee engagement in the airline industry.	The application of SET impacts the relationship between selecting and recruiting, training and development, and organizational performance through employee engagement as a mediating variable.
2. (Pandita and Ray 2018)	Industrial and Commercial Training.	Talent management and employee engagement—a meta-analysis of their impact on talent retention.	The synchronization of talent management practices and employee engagement initiatives improves talent retention
3. Bakker & Leiter, 2017	Organizational Dynamics Volume 46, Issue 2, April–June 2017	Strategic and proactive approaches to work	A top-down approach may involve implementing strategic human resource management (HRM) systems to facilitate work engagement, or making their leaders aware of the need for job resources for employees. Self-management, job crafting, strengths use, and mobilizing ego resources are all possible bottom-up approaches to work engagement.
4. Joo et al.,2017	The Journal of Applied Behavioural Science.	Work Cognition and Psychological Well-Being: The Role of Cognitive Engagement as a Partial Mediator	A structural equation model showed that perceived work cognitions accounted for 31% of cognitive engagement variance among 518 employees. Further, 50% of the variance in psychological well-being was explained by employees' work cognition and cognitive engagement.
5. Babakus et al., 2017.	International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management	Work engagement and turnover intentions: Correlates and customer orientation as a moderator.	In a study conducted with employees in the hotel industry in North Cyprus, training was negatively correlated with EE.
6. Presbitero, A. (2017). .	Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality & Tourism	How do changes in human resource management practices influence employee engagement? A longitudinal study in a hotel chain in the Philippines	The effect of training and development shows a positive effect on employee engagement
7. Alfes et al.,2016)	Personnel Review, vol. 45 no. 6;	Testing additive versus interactive effects of person-organization fit and organizational trust on engagement and performance	The interactive model predicted work engagement better than the additive model, for engaged employees felt close fit with their organization and trusted it. Further, engagement mediated the relationship between the interaction and task performance.
8. (Karatepe & Olugbade, 2016.	International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management.	The mediating role of work engagement in the relationship between high-performance work practices and job outcomes of employees in Nigeria.	High-performance work systems (HPWS) have an effect on employee engagement and extra-role performance.
9. (Albrecht et al. 2015)	Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance,	Employee engagement, human resource management practices and competitive advantage	All aspects of the employer-employee relationship and the employee lifecycle should be focused on engagement. Engaging practices, processes, and systems need to be strategically embedded throughout selection,

			socialization, performance management, and training and development.
10. Fletcher, L. (2015).	Human Resource Development International.	Training perceptions, engagement, and performance: Comparing work engagement and personal role engagement.	Personal role engagement has correlation between training perceptions and task proficiency, as well as training perceptions and task adaptability.
11. Rana, S, (2015).	Human Resource Development International	High-involvement work practices and employee engagement	A highly engaged workforce requires the following: (a) empowerment (b) information on diverse organizational issues, (c) a tangible reward system, and (d) knowledge about resources and opportunities to develop skills.
12. Guest, D. E (2014).	Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance	Employee engagement: A sceptical analysis.	Human resources professionals should be able to use evidence-based selection processes to identify among applicants those who will be most engaged on the job if they want to hire energetic, dedicated, and goal-oriented employees.
13. (Saks & Gruman, 2014).	Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance	Making organizations more effective through organizational socialization.	The resource-based approach to socialization has been proposed as a meaningful way to improve newcomer adjustment and socialization, as well as to understand how to engage.
14. (Townsend et al., 2014)	International Journal of Human Resource Management	Routes to partial success: collaborative employment relations and employee engagement	Engagement as a management practice or intervention lies more squarely within the established field of interest around participation and involvement. Future developments in this area have great potential, combining practitioners' concerns with the longstanding traditions of industrial relations scholars
15. (Ling et al. 2014).	International Journal of Culture, Tourism and Hospitality Research	An empirical investigation into the influence of human resource management practices on work engagement: The case of customer-contact employees in Malaysia	Through their study authors found out that there is a positive significant influence of training and performance on work engagement.
16. (Arrowsmith & Parker, 2013).	The international journal of Human Resource management, 24(14), 2692-2712.	The meaning of 'employee engagement' for the values and roles of the HRM function.	An analysis of organizational engagement initiatives within one firm reveals tensions, multiple departments and ambiguities, and illustrates that engagement is not a static, value-free construct. HR professionals need political astuteness and commitment to implement engagement initiatives.
17. (Alfes et al. 2013)	Human resource management, 52(6), 839-859.	The relationship between line manager behaviour, perceived HRM practices, and individual performance: Examining the mediating role of engagement	Employee engagement is correlated with perceived HRM practices and line manager behaviour. Furthermore, employee engagement has a strong correlation with individual performance and fully mediates the relationship between perceived HRM practices and perceived line manager behaviour, as well as self-reported task performance and innovative work behaviour.

18. (Rurkkhum and Bartlett 2012)	Human Resource Development International	The relationship between employee engagement and organizational citizenship behaviour in Thailand	Engagement affects organizational citizenship behaviour, but perceptions of HRD have no moderating effect
19. Shuck et, al, 2012).	Human Resource Development Review	The jingle jangle of employee engagement: Further exploration of the emerging construct and implications for workplace learning and performance.	For the development of workplace learning and performance interventions, it is important to understand the theory behind relationships between the constructs
20. (Inceoglu & Warr, 2011).	Journal of Personnel Psychology	Personality and job engagement	understanding the links between selection practices and engagement is under researched (Inceoglu & Warr, 2011);
21. (Tett & Burnett2003).	Journal of Applied Psychology	A personality trait-based interactionist model of job performance.	Selecting for engagement will only be relevant if the organizational context supports personality traits most predictive of engagement.

The association between HRM and engagement is diverse ranging from learning, training and high impact services to socialization and mediates the relationship between perceived HRM practices and perceived line manager behaviour. One study cites the potential of interventions on employee engagement. (Townend, et.al, 2014)

2.2 Antecedents of Engagement in General a Comparative Analysis:

We collated the antecedents of employee engagement from four literature reviews based on abstract and theoretical implications. They include (Wollard and Shuck, 2010) identified 42 individual and organizational antecedents of employee engagement. Similarly, (Bailey et al., 2017) identified 155 empirical studies included reference to the antecedents of engagement. These were grouped into five categories Individual psychological states(52 studies) ; Experienced job-design-related factors(65 studies) , Perceived leadership and management (36 studies); Perception of Organizational support(POS) Individual and organizational (53 studies) and Organizational intervention and activities(9 studies).Additionally , (Lee et al, 2017) details 24 antecedents as Job Resources(10), POS(3), leadership and management(2), Training Interventions(2) and Meaningful work(5) among others.

In addition, synthesis of empirical studies from Integrative review by(Shuck et. al 2011) stated Individual psychological states(5 studies),POS(3 studies),Leadership(1 studies) , Job design(2 studies)represented through the third bar chart The review indicates the popularity of the JD-R model which is reflected through the number of studies on Job design. However, research on Individual perceptions of team and organizational factors or perceived organizational support is limited. However, there are limited just ten studies which focus into the industrial or HRM aspects linked to engagement.

Fig.4: Comparative Analysis of EE

First Bar graph depicts review from (Bailey et.al, 2017), the second from (Lee et.al, 2017) and third from (Shuck and Wollard, 2011) and numbers indicate articles under different subjects.

2.3 Antecedents of Engagement in IT: A total of 16 studies were detailed in the antecedents of EE in Table-2

Author	Year	Title & Journal	EE Antecedents	Category
1. Sharma & Nambudiri	2020	Work engagement, job crafting and innovativeness in the Indian IT industry. Personnel Review.	Stronger the Perception of supervisory support stronger would be the relationship between work engagement and employee’s job crafting behaviour	Job Design
2.Tiwari and Lenka,	2019	Employee engagement: study of survivors in Indian IT/ITES sector, IIMB Management Review (2019)	that internal corporate communication, knowledge sharing, continuous learning, intrapreneurship, and perceived communication satisfaction were positively associated with employee engagement; JOB resources; HRM;POS	Job Design; POS;HRM
3.Rana & Sharma,	2019	Impact of employer branding on job engagement and organizational commitment in Indian IT sector. International Journal of Risk and Contingency Management (IJRCM)	A positive association exists between employer branding and job-engagement	POS
4.Al-dalahmeh& Khalaf	2018	The effect of employee engagement on organizational performance via the mediating role of job satisfaction: The case of IT employees in Jordanian banking sector. Modern Applied Science	vigour provided job satisfaction; vigour, absorption &dedication contributed to Organizational performance	Job Design
5.Jalaja and Padashetty,	2018	Employee experience in building employee engagement: An employee perspective. International Journal of Research in Economics and Social Sciences	Organizational climate, internal policies and leadership as main antecedents for employee experience and significant impact of employee experience on EE	Perceived Leadership Support;
6.Ugargol, & Patrick	2018	The relationship of workplace flexibility to employee engagement among information technology employees in India. South Asian Journal of Human Resources Management,	Flexible Work Arrangement were positively related to EE	Perceived Organizational Support & JDR

7.Garg & Malik	2017	"Learning organization and Work engagement: Exploring the nexus in Indian IT sector", Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration	Vigour and dedication were most significantly predicted by embedded system and continuous learning opportunities of learning organization	Job Design
8.Prabhakar & Reddy	2016	Employee Engagement in the IT Industry–Evidence from India. Strategic Management Quarterly	Organizational Support ,Intrinsic Motivators ; POS: Employee oriented organizational culture ;Distributive justice ;HRM: Effective goal-setting ;Hygiene elements ;Appraisal Transparency ;Customized Training ;Feedback and Peer Cohesiveness	Job Design
9.Bhuvanaiah and Raya	2016	Predicting employee work engagement levels, determinants and performance outcome: Empirical validation in the context of an information technology organization. Global Business Review.	Organizational Culture has an overarching effect on engagement behaviours of employees	POS
10.De Clercq et al.,	2014	Servant leadership and work engagement: The contingency effects of leader–follower social capital. Human Resource Development Quarterly.	While servant leadership has an effect on work engagement	Perceived Leadership Support;
11Gan and Gan	2014	Sequential development among dimensions of job burnout and engagement among IT employees. Stress and Health	Positive association between job resources and the three dimensions of engagement; Positive association of extraversion and conscientiousness with engagement directly and indirectly via job resources. Personal Resources & Job Demand	Job-design
12Sawang .S	2012	There is an inverted U-shaped relationship between job demands and work engagement: the moderating role of social support? International Journal of Man- power,	Job demands and social support have been found to be positively associated with engagement.	Job Design
13.Bhatnagar. J	2012	Management of innovation: Role of psychological empowerment, work engagement and turnover intention in the Indian context. The International Journal of Human Resource Management.	Psychological empowerment was found to have strong predictive power on work engagement and innovation	Job Design
14.Braine & Roodt	2011	The job demands–resources model as predictor of work identity and work engagement: a comparative analysis. S African J Ind Psychology 2011	Positive association exists between job resources and engagement	Job Design
15.Chen et al.	2011	Chen, Z.J., Zhang, X. and Vogel, D. (2011). Exploring the underlying processes between conflict and knowledge sharing: a work–engagement perspective. Journal of Applied Social Psychology		POS
16.Hallberg and Schaufeli	2006	Same same but different? Can work engagement be discriminated from job involvement and organizational commitment? European Psychologist	Positive association of autonomy and feedback with engagement	Job Design

Our own review on engagement in IT of 16 empirical studies is in alignment with other literature reviews on employee engagement. Job Design as antecedent for 10 studies, POS (3 studies),Leadership(2 studies),HRM(1 studies) as antecedent of employee engagement. Efforts to improve employee engagement can be complicated and disillusioning when there is a never-ending list of antecedents. To customize engagement with context, features of job design, POS, and individual psychological states need to be examined in much greater detail. Engagement-driving interventions have not been observed in our review on IT.

Figure 5. Depicts the description statistics of Table-2

2.4 Analyzing the Need for Talent Acquisition Experience and Service quality in IT:

2.4.1: Importance and Challenges of Recruitment & Selection in Indian IT:

Employees are the face and mirrored image of any organization's selection process (Tyler, 2005; Barclay, 2001). As competition increases, particularly in the IT sector, Organizations are struggling to source highly skilled individuals who will meet the technical and functional needs of the work and fit with the organization's values. Organizations compete fiercely for the right talent (Dries, 2013; Michaels et al., 2001) as every organization perceives that a talented workforce contributes to organizational performance (Collings and Mellahi, 2013). HRM leaders spend about 80 per cent of their time on recruitment and selection (Grossman, 2006). Organizations are uncertain about applicants' acceptance of job offers until they physically join (Grossman, 2006; Agrawal and Thite, 2003). Further, the job attrition rate is around 15-20 per cent, amplified at the lower and mid-management levels (Friedmann et al., 2008). In India, most IT job seekers receive multiple job offers and are spoilt for choice (Rao, P.2010). Therefore, to remain attractive to the talent pool, IT firms have to communicate that they are a 'great place to work' (Kavitha and Srinivasan, 2012) and need to provide working contexts that provide a good "fit" between the role expectations of prospective employees and their subsequent working environment for retaining high calibre, high achieving, productive, committed and "engaged" employees. (Herriot, 2002; Morgeson and Dierdorff, 2011)

Additionally, HR managers have to be very particular in providing an exceptional candidate experience rooted in the organization's culture while ensuring the quality of hire. This enables to sustain the firm's competitive advantage and ensures smooth functioning (Gatewood, 1993; Vance, 2006; Bagga and Srivastava, 2014; Singh, 2018; Das and Kodwani, 2018)

2.4.2. Examining TA experience using Service quality framework

Service management works to amplify organizations' offerings creating service value through customer interaction Groenroos, C. (1994; 2006). For this review, we can examine the quality criteria for the candidate selection process from three main perspectives, based on the model proposed by (Uen et al., 2005; Crick and Spencer, 2011). TA service quality would comprise different objectives for inputs, processes and outcomes. Further, output service quality would include short-listed candidates accepting the job offer. For the remaining candidates, perceptions will shape future relationships as: customer, investor, and future applicant (Cascio & Boudreau, 2011; Miles & McCamay, 2018). Thus, the output would measure innovativeness, comprehensiveness, and customization (Johnson et al., 1995; Uen et al., 2005). Similarly, Process service quality entails the reliability and responsiveness of interactions at different points of the recruitment life cycle (Johnson et al., 1995). For example, Individuals looking for work with a technological firm reported their impressions of the firm's website usability and perceived likeness to their recruiter, organizational trustworthiness and trust, and intent to accept a job offer (Kedarnath et al., 2020). Additionally, HR input service quality would comprise the structure of the workflow for processes, and information, for example, business analytics and intelligence (Cruz-Jesus et al., 2019), human resource information system (HRIS); (Shah Alam et al., 2011; E-HRM (McDonald et al., 2017; Rahman et al., 2018), social recruiting (Kashi et al., 2016), and competence of business requirements (Uen et al., 2005). The efficiency and performance of the TA process will improve with the adoption of AI Technology (Upadhyay and Khandelwal, 2018; Karaboga et al., 2020). All these three factors of service quality have a compounding effect in creating recruitment perceptions of 'the good place to work, leading to attraction & subsequent engagement. Lastly, HR processes are perceived differently by the employee and their managers (Wang. et al., 2020)

3.1 DISCUSSION

This integrative review aims to augment our understanding of talent acquisition experience and EE. Therefore, we examined 95 empirical and conceptual studies and literature reviews at the intersection of HRM and engagement, talent acquisition and service quality. The studies reveal positive psychology has influenced EE evolution as a motivational construct. Further, (Shuck et al., 2017) have positioned EE as an outcome, state and process. Thus, EE has the flexibility to be contextualized to align and integrate across multiple organizational functions, such as Human resources management, marketing, and service quality management, thereby providing a strategic view. This broader focus enables the dual requirement of attracting the right quality of talent and subsequently building a relationship during the hiring process leading to engagement and retention. Thus TA experience creates service value structured around meaningfulness and safety in Kahn's (1990) engagement model evolving into vigour.

Additionally, Organizational interventions accounted for eleven out of 155 antecedents on EE. For example, Leroy et al. (2013) research found training and development had a positive impact on EE. Similarly, fifty-nine studies examined the role of perceived organization support (POS) on EE. Further, our synthesis and integration of theoretical frameworks on social exchange,

engagement, and service quality and talent acquisition have combined to provide a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between TA experience, service quality, and employee engagement. It is evident from the antecedents of EE and TA that candidate interactions, perceptions, and decisions to continue the relationship during the recruitment process and thereafter in employment mirror the assumptions of SET and talent supply chain theory (Saks, 2006, Cascio & Boudreau, 2011; Miles & McCamay, 2018). HR service quality theory and COR (Conservation of Resources) explain the rationale behind adequate resources and POS in creating service value for the candidates and influencing their perception. Similarly, TA inputs, processes and outputs examine the objectivity that increases meaningfulness and attraction, leading to a commitment to pursue the recruitment process. (Hobfoll, 2001; Uen et al., 2005; Crick and Spencer, 2011).

These findings indicate that POS, and SET shapes the perception of candidate experience, and may result in subsequent engagement. However, they have to manage as a process and not left to the individual recruiter. Thus, our review highlights the association between TA, a routine practice of HRM and its service value by incorporating aspects of the engagement as the management process and Kahn's (1990) model of personal role engagement in a human capital-intensive IT sector.

Findings from three studies (Bishop 2013); Brummelhuis et al. 2012; Carter et al. 2010) suggest that there is considerable potential for employers to take creative steps to foster and enhance employee engagement in implementing such interventions. Thus, there is a need to quantitatively prove nexus and explore avenues of engagement as a management practice.

3.2 Theoretical Contribution:

How are the findings of transdisciplinary studies related to each other?

The review synthesizes and proposes integration between constituents of social exchange instrument theory (Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005); talent supply chain theory (Cascio & Boudreau, 2011; Miles & McCamay, 2018), the output of service quality and engagement (Kahn, 1990; Crick and Spencer, 2011; Lambert et al., 2021). Through this integrated model, engagement can be operationalized as a practice construct by reducing the perceived differences between HR and candidates resulting in positive experience throughout the recruitment cycle that promote loyalty and commitment. Thereby substantiating EE intervention to address Fineman's (2006) scepticism that positive psychologists have failed to consider the social, economic, and political context that leads to helplessness at work.

Hence, we propose our model as a suggested way forward:

Fig 6: Integrated Model: Integrating Job Aspirant Experience with Employee Engagement

The proposed model articulates service value through adapting principles of SERVQUAL (Parasuraman et. al, 1988) parameters of reliability, responsiveness, empathy, and trust ; impact of SET (Guan et.al, 2020), Talent supply chain(Miles& McCain, 2018) and engagement and service-profit chain(Lambert et.al, 2021)on interfaces throughout the recruitment cycle. Thus, creating and managing perceived meaningfulness, safety, and quality during the interaction leading to acceptance of job offer and subsequent commitment and engagement. Even those not selected will continue the relationship (e.g. positive posts on social media, advocacy, and future applicant).Further, it strengthens both (Khan, 1990; Sak, 2006) model for engagement.

Additionally, the proposed framework suggests possibilities for resolving the missing link between TA and EE (Inceoglu, I., & Warr, P, 2011), and building congruence between the candidate and recruiter’s perception on TA experience.

3.3 Implication for Researchers

Thus, the current review adds new dimension to the current knowledge on impact of HRM on EE ((Alola and Alafeshat 2021; Pandita and Ray, 2018) and engagement as a management practice (Bailey. Et. al, 2018) by exploring service quality mechanisms with TA process to impact candidate experience and subsequent EE. Additionally, this review fulfils the existing research gap between employee engagement and talent acquisition experience in IT industry by focusing on possible linkages between the two (Inceoglu & Warr, 2011).Secondly,

synthesizing social exchange theory shapes organizational exchanges leading to loyalty, obligation, and engagement (Tsui et al., 1997; Saks, 2006; Agarwal, 2014; Kim & Park, 2017). Further, we have been able to add perspective through the application of a service quality framework and trust, we have been able to suggest ways to manage social interfaces between the candidate and the recruitment team at different stages of the recruitment cycle, evolving from meaningful exchanges leading to increased vigour. Thirdly, our theoretical framework posits that recruiting and EE processes are integrated and managed to create common understanding between the recruiter and recruit perspectives. Consequently, long-term relationship and engagement are strengthened based on appraisal alignment. Thus integrating transdisciplinary theoretical perspective from HRM, service quality aligning multiple functions within organization. This broader view of EE has the potential to benefit the existing literature on organizational psychology, HRM, service quality, marketing, thereby providing perspective. Future studies may examine the impact of other aspects of HRM on EE, Employee Value Proposition and strategy.

3.4 Implications for Practitioners

HR and business leaders can explore the proposed TA framework as a roadmap to gain insights into the recruitment cycle and provide the requisite tools and resources to manage the factors that drive a firm's TA experience and subsequent EE. Therefore, creating a blueprint that incorporates candidate and recruiter perspective thereby addresses the organization attractiveness, uncertainty of candidates joining the company, and subsequent EE.

Secondly, management of the talent acquisition is process driven rather than solely recruiter driven.

Thirdly, we operationalize TA experience have posited EE as a management practice construct that meets motivational and hygiene needs. As a result, the candidate feels valued, leading to acceptance of the job offer and subsequent loyalty and commitment. Furthermore, the blueprint increases understanding of TA's impact on the organization's attractiveness, process credibility, and subsequent EE. For example, perceived work cognitions accounted for 31% of the variance in cognitive engagement. (Joo et al., 2017. This approach addresses HR managers' long-felt need to integrate engagement research into HR operational processes, such as TA instead of annual surveys (Albrecht et al., 2015). Moreover, little practitioner focus is devoted to understanding the connection between EE and recruitment practices (Inceoglu & Warr, 2011; Mäkikangas et al., 2013), and increasing candidate and recruiter congruence. Additionally, it could further explore branding as a 'good place to work, and employee value proposition through the proposed framework.

3.5 Conclusion:

These are some of the probable inferences that can be drawn from the review. First, in an IT job market where most job openings are homogenous, exceptional TA service could be a unique competitive advantage for firms. Second, HR practitioners and researchers have a new management practice construct of EE to be explored and validated through a practical

enterprise-wide set of dynamic, technology-mediated, HR and candidate-centric, evidence-based service quality frameworks. Third, building congruence between the candidate search process and the HR recruitment process may build association and reduce applicant attrition, value and meaningfulness during the recruitment interface, which may lead to obligation, loyalty and engagement. Lastly, our theoretical construct is crucial for fostering further strategic and transdisciplinary research incorporating EE has the potential for creating an employee value proposition, the connection between HRM and EE, and branding within a human capital-intensive IT sector.

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